

UNDERSTANDING MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES THROUGH HEATMAP ANALYSIS OF ONLINE TEACHING EXPERIENCE CORRELATIONS**A.K. Jumasseitova,***PhD, professor,*

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Abstract

This article explores the experiences and perceptions of online teaching among instructors from higher education institutions in Kazakhstan. Through a comprehensive survey, data were collected from educators across various disciplines, including social sciences, natural sciences, engineering, medical fields, and more, to examine the factors influencing the acceptance of online learning. The survey covered demographic characteristics, teaching experience, satisfaction with online teaching performance, and digital competence. It also assessed the technological skills of instructors, their ability to use various online platforms, and their engagement with students in an online environment. Additionally, challenges such as internet connectivity, access to resources, and institutional support were analyzed.

The results highlight significant gender disparity, with a higher representation of female instructors, and show that most instructors were experienced in online teaching before the pandemic. Spearman's correlation coefficient was employed to identify the strongest positive and negative correlations between key variables. Positive correlations emphasized the importance of technical proficiency and diverse teaching methods, while negative correlations revealed challenges related to gender inclusivity in mixed-gender online classes.

A heat map was used to visualize these correlations, allowing for quick identification of key trends. The findings suggest that technical skills, institutional support, and inclusivity play crucial roles in shaping instructors' experiences of online teaching. This article concludes that improving technical training, fostering inclusivity, and enhancing institutional support will be key to improving the quality of online education in Kazakhstan.

Keywords: management, economic analysis, online education, heatmap analysis

Introduction

Experience with online education has become an inevitable part of the education system. The first steps were taken by universities during the unexpected COVID-19 pandemic. This experience is significant, and the data collected helps us understand the attitudes of both academic staff and students. Bueckle and Börner (2017) further contribute to this understanding by reviewing the design of learning analytics dashboards and proposing a multi-level heat map to track student engagement and performance. Their research highlights the role of visual tools in enhancing the online learning experience.

Rodriguez-Segura et al. (2020) expand on these insights by examining emergency remote teaching (ERT) in Mexico, focusing on the use of Microsoft Teams. They emphasize the importance of understanding student satisfaction in online learning environments, identifying correlations between satisfaction factors through the use of heat maps.

Similarly, Jiang et al. (2021) investigate the factors influencing student satisfaction with online platforms in China. They apply the Technology Satisfaction Model and find that self-efficacy, ease of use, and regional differences play key roles in shaping satisfaction with online learning.

Means et al. (2009) add to this body of research by conducting a meta-analysis of online versus face-to-face learning, finding that students in online or blended learning environments generally perform better than

those in traditional settings. However, the positive effects of blended learning are linked to additional instructional time rather than the medium itself, particularly highlighting the scarcity of rigorous studies for K-12 students.

Together, these studies emphasize the complex factors impacting online education, including student satisfaction, teaching methods, and the design of learning tools.

Our study has a survey was conducted among instructors teaching in an online learning environment. The participants were educators from various higher education institutions in Kazakhstan, representing a diverse range of subject areas. This approach allowed for the collection of comprehensive data regarding their experiences and perceptions of online education. The surveyed disciplines included social sciences, natural sciences, engineering, medical and health-related fields, and more, providing a broad perspective on the challenges and factors influencing the acceptance of online learning. The questionnaire used in this study was designed to gather comprehensive information from instructors on various aspects of online teaching. The questions covered demographic factors such as gender and age, as well as the instructors' teaching experience and subject areas. Additionally, the survey explored the instructors' prior experience with online teaching, their satisfaction with their performance, and their level of digital competence in navigating and utilizing online teaching tools and platforms. Further sec-

tions of the questionnaire assessed the instructors' technological skills, including the ability to communicate with students using various platforms, handle digital files, and use synchronous and asynchronous tools for teaching. The survey also addressed the instructors' perceptions of online learning, including their motivation, teaching strategies, and engagement with students in the online environment. The challenges faced by instructors, such as technical issues, access to resources, and support from institutions, were also explored. Instructors were asked about their experiences with internet connectivity, access to devices, and the sufficiency of support provided by their universities. Lastly, the questionnaire examined the instructors' views on the future of online learning and their suggestions for improving the quality of online education.

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the profile of the instructors who participated in the study, an analysis of their demographic characteristics was conducted. These data provide insights into the representation of different groups of instructors in online teaching and help to better understand how their characteristics may influence their perceptions and experiences of online education.

Gender: The sample showed a significant gender disparity, with approximately 70% of respondents identifying as female, while about 30% identified as male. This indicates a higher representation of female instructors, which aligns with broader trends in the education sector (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1

Age Range: The age distribution revealed that the largest group of participants were aged 55 and over (approximately 25%), followed closely by those aged 35-44 (around 25%). A smaller portion of respondents

were between 25 and 34 years old, with very few participants aged 18-24. This suggests that the majority of instructors are mid- to late-career professionals (*Figure 2*).

Figure 2

Level of Students Taught: The majority of respondents (around 60%) reported teaching undergraduate students. About 30% indicated that they teach both

undergraduate and postgraduate students, while a smaller proportion of instructors worked exclusively with postgraduate students (*Figure 3*).

Figure 3

Subject Areas: The participants represented a broad range of academic disciplines. The most common field was food and agricultural sciences, followed by engineering and biological sciences. There was also

significant representation from medical sciences and social sciences, reflecting a wide diversity of subject areas (Figure 4).

Figure 4

Experience in Online Teaching: Approximately 80% of the instructors had prior experience teaching online courses, indicating that most participants were familiar with online education technologies before the

pandemic. The remaining 20% had no such experience, highlighting the importance of additional training and support for these educators (Figure 5).

Figure 5

Spearman's correlation coefficient was utilized to examine the relationships between key variables. This method was chosen for its robustness in handling non-parametric data, which is common in survey responses. The use of correlation analysis in social and economic research is widespread. For instance, Golovchin (2019) applied Pearson's linear correlation to examine the relationship between internet activity and social well-being in a regional population. His findings demonstrated an inverse relationship between increased internet usage and satisfaction with various aspects of life, thus

highlighting the importance of correlation analysis in understanding complex societal behaviors

Based on the calculated correlation coefficients, a heat map was created to visually assess the relationships between different survey questions (Figure 6). This map allows for a clear evaluation of the strength of correlations between variables. The color scheme—dark red indicating strong positive correlations, light blue representing weak negative correlations, and shades of light red or pale blue for weaker correlations—helps to quickly identify key associations. As

part of the study, the 10 strongest positive and 10 strongest negative correlations were identified.

Correlations

Figure 6

Heat maps have become an indispensable tool for visualizing complex data, particularly in the fields of sociological research and decision support systems (DSS). Their primary advantage lies in their ability to make multidimensional data easy to interpret, providing a clear representation of relationships between different variables. By using a gradient of colors, ranging from strong red for positive correlations and light blue for negative correlations, heat maps enable researchers to quickly identify key trends, patterns, and associations within datasets. Lightly shaded areas represent weaker or no correlations, allowing the viewer to focus on the most significant interactions. This kind of visualization not only aids experts in their analysis but also makes data more accessible to non-expert stakeholders, facilitating informed decision-making across different fields.

In sociological and educational studies, heat maps are particularly useful for analyzing survey data. They allow researchers to visualize correlations between responses to different questions, which can offer valuable insights into how various factors influence participants' behaviors, perceptions, and outcomes. Based on the calculated correlation coefficients, the heat map provides a visual assessment of the relationships between different questions. The color scheme of the map helps to quickly identify strong and weak correlations: dark red represents strong positive correlations, light blue shows weak negative correlations, and light shades indicate less pronounced or absent connections. This allows for an efficient analysis of how variables interact with each other, enhancing the decision-making process.

A notable example of heat map application is found in the study 'Survey Assessment for Decision Support Using Self-Organizing Maps Profile Characterization with an Odds and Cluster Heat Map'. In this research, self-organizing maps (SOM) were used to identify respondent profiles based on their survey answers, and heat maps were employed to visualize the strength of the relationships between these profiles and various survey questions. The study demonstrated that

heat maps can play a key role in supporting decision-making processes by providing a clear, visual summary of complex statistical data. This is especially important in decision support systems, where stakeholders need quick and accurate interpretations of data to inform strategic decisions.

One of the key strengths of heat maps is their ability to present both the magnitude and direction of correlations in a format that is easy to interpret. For example, a researcher can immediately identify which survey responses are most strongly correlated with specific demographic characteristics, such as gender or educational background. This feature is particularly useful in multidisciplinary fields, where decision-makers may need to consider a wide range of variables to understand how different factors interact and influence outcomes.

The utility of heat maps in DSS also extends beyond academia. In policy-making, urban planning, and education management, decision-makers can use heat maps to rapidly assess public opinion, stakeholder feedback, or student satisfaction. By condensing large amounts of data into a visual format, heat maps provide a strategic advantage in settings where timely and informed decisions are crucial.

In summary, heat maps are a powerful tool for visualizing and analyzing survey data. They enhance the decision-making process by offering a clear, intuitive way to interpret complex relationships between variables. The study by Abarca-Alvarez et al. further illustrates the practical applications of heat maps in DSS, showcasing their ability to facilitate the interpretation of high-dimensional data and improve the accuracy of decisions made in response to survey findings (Entropy).

As part of the study, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was employed to analyze the relationships between various factors influencing the acceptance of online learning among instructors. This method allowed us to identify both positive and negative associations between key variables. Specifically, the analysis revealed the 10 strongest positive and 10 strongest negative correlations.

Table 1

The 10 Strongest Positive Correlations Identified in the Study of Online Teaching Experiences

№	Question 1	Question 2	Level of Correlation
1	I am able to use synchronous technologies (Skype, Zoom, MS Teams) and asynchronous technologies (discussion boards, email) to communicate and engage with students in online courses	I know how to add course materials to different online platforms adopted by the university, such as Learning Management System (LMS)	0,82
2	I can post quizzes and exams on different platforms adopted by the university such as Learning Management System (LMS)	I know how to add course materials to different online platforms adopted by the university, such as Learning Management System (LMS)	0,83
3	I can provide feedback and mark students' coursework on different platforms adopted by the university such as Learning Management System (LMS)	I can post quizzes and exams on different platforms adopted by the university such as Learning Management System (LMS)	0,78
4	The course was designed to use an array of course content delivery methods, such as live classes, group discussions, and written tasks	The course employed multiple assessment methods, such as oral exams, take-home work, online class exams, and group projects	0,77
5	I can download a file attached to an e-mail message to a local disk and attach a file to an e-mail message from a local disk and send it off	I am knowledgeable in searching for the information related to a course via the internet	0,79
6	I am able to use synchronous technologies (Skype, Zoom, MS Teams) and asynchronous technologies (discussion boards, email) to communicate and engage with students in online courses	I am knowledgeable in searching for the information related to a course via the internet	0,73
7	I am able to use synchronous technologies (Skype, Zoom, MS Teams) and asynchronous technologies (discussion boards, email) to communicate and engage with students in online courses	I can download a file attached to an e-mail message to a local disk and attach a file to an e-mail message from a local disk and send it off	0,73
8	I used a diversity of methods to explain the course materials and used different tasks during the online class to encourage students to relate the knowledge with work or outside life	The course employed multiple assessment methods, such as oral exams, take-home work, online class exams, and group projects	0,69
9	The course employed multiple assessment methods, such as oral exams, take-home work, online class exams, and group projects	The course was designed to use an array of course content delivery methods, such as live classes, group discussions, and written tasks	0,74
10	I can download a file attached to an e-mail message to a local disk and attach a file to an e-mail message from a local disk and send it off	I am able to use synchronous technologies (Skype, Zoom, MS Teams) and asynchronous technologies (discussion boards, email) to communicate and engage with students in online courses	0,73

Table 2

The 10 Strongest Negative Correlations Identified in the Study of Online Teaching Experiences

№	Question 1	Question 2	Level of Correlation
1	I do not interact (e.g. asking or answering questions to another gender) effectively in mixed-gender online courses	I used a diversity of methods to explain the course materials and used different tasks during the online class to encourage students to relate the knowledge with work or outside life	-0,28
2	I would prefer NOT to teach an online course that includes both male and female students in the future	I used a diversity of methods to explain the course materials and used different tasks during the online class to encourage students to relate the knowledge with work or outside life	-0,36
3	I feel generally uncomfortable if online classes include male and female students	I engage fully with online teaching because I enjoy it, and it is more attractive and interesting to me than face-to-face teaching	-0,25
4	I would prefer NOT to teach an online course that includes both male and female students in the future	Compared to face-to-face classes, when I engage in online teaching, I feel more motivated in involving myself in different teaching activities, especially interactive discussions with students to enhance their understanding of the course material	-0,38
5	I feel generally uncomfortable if online classes include male and female students	When I engage in online teaching, I would have difficulties investing my knowledge gained from outside of class to use in the online class to enhance knowledge and students engagement	-0,23
6	I do not interact (e.g. asking or answering questions to another gender) effectively in mixed-gender online courses	When I engage in online teaching, I would have difficulties investing my knowledge gained from outside of class to use in the online class to enhance knowledge and students engagement	-0,23
7	I feel generally uncomfortable if online classes include male and female students	In my experience, the internet connectivity is stable and sufficient for teaching online classes, communicating with students, and performing teaching tasks	-0,21
8	I do not interact (e.g. asking or answering questions to another gender) effectively in mixed-gender online courses	In my experience, the internet connectivity is stable and sufficient for teaching online classes, communicating with students, and performing teaching tasks	-0,2
9	I feel generally uncomfortable if online classes include male and female students	As an instructor, I faced difficulties obtaining my own laptop or device to teach online classes, communicate with students, and perform teaching tasks	-0,19
10	I do not interact (e.g. asking or answering questions to another gender) effectively in mixed-gender online courses	As an instructor, I faced difficulties obtaining my own laptop or device to teach online classes, communicate with students, and perform teaching tasks	-0,18

Positive Correlations

The high positive correlations identified in this study highlight the strong relationship between various aspects of technical proficiency and the use of teaching methods in online learning. Below are some of the most significant positive correlations.

1. **Technical skills and working with learning platforms (0.82 and 0.83):**Instructors who are proficient in using synchronous and asynchronous technologies to interact with students also possess the knowledge to upload materials onto various learning platforms, such as Learning Management Systems (LMS). This underscores the importance of mastering different technologies for effective online teaching.

2. **Creating and conducting tests and exams (0.78):**The ability of instructors to administer tests and

exams on different platforms is closely related to their ability to add instructional materials to these platforms. This indicates that technical skills are crucial for assessing students' knowledge in an online setting.

3. **Diversity of teaching methods and knowledge assessment (0.77):**Courses that use a variety of content delivery and assessment methods, such as live classes, group discussions, and written tasks, enhance students' understanding and retention of the material. This highlights the importance of using diverse methods to improve the quality of learning.

Negative Correlations

The strong negative correlations point to significant challenges that instructors face when teaching online courses in mixed-gender settings. Below are the most notable negative correlations.

1. **Reluctance to teach mixed-gender groups (-0.36):**Instructors who are reluctant to teach in mixed-gender groups tend to use fewer diverse methods to explain instructional materials and complete tasks. This may be due to discomfort or difficulties managing mixed-gender groups.

2. **Discomfort with mixed-gender teaching and teaching engagement (-0.25 and -0.38):**Instructors who experience discomfort when teaching mixed-gender groups are less engaged in the teaching process and less motivated to use interactive methods. This underscores the need for creating a more inclusive educational environment.

3. **Difficulties in interaction and teaching (-0.23 and -0.21):**Instructors who face challenges interacting with the opposite gender are also less confident in their ability to effectively use external knowledge and improve engagement in online teaching. This indicates the need for training in gender inclusivity.

Support and Development of Diverse Teaching Methods

1. **Training and skill development for instructors:**Universities should invest in training instructors so that they can effectively use diverse teaching methods and adapt to various conditions. This includes regular training on technology use and teaching methodologies.

2. **Development of inclusive instructional materials:**The creation of instructional materials that account for gender aspects and foster a comfortable learning environment for all students is essential. It is important to develop materials that encourage the engagement of all students, regardless of gender.

3. **Workshops and training on inclusivity:**Regular workshops and training for instructors on gender inclusivity and interaction in mixed-gender groups should be conducted. This will help instructors feel more confident and comfortable when working with mixed-gender groups.

Support for Technical and Financial Needs

1. **Provision of access to necessary resources:**Universities should ensure that instructors have access to necessary devices and software, as well as support them in covering internet service costs. This will help instructors avoid technical difficulties and focus on the teaching process.

2. **Creation of centralized technical support services:**Developing efficient support services that can promptly address the technical and financial issues faced by instructors is crucial. This includes providing consultations on technical matters and assistance in resolving personal problems related to online teaching.

Conclusion

This paper sheds light on several critical factors that influence instructors' acceptance and experiences of online teaching in higher education institutions in Kazakhstan. The findings suggest that technical proficiency, the availability of resources, and gender inclusivity play pivotal roles in shaping instructors' satisfaction and performance in an online learning environment.

Positive Correlations and Technical Skills

The results reveal that technical skills are crucial for effective online teaching. Strong positive correlations, such as those between proficiency in using synchronous technologies and the ability to add course materials to platforms like Learning Management Systems (LMS), underscore the importance of comprehensive training in digital tools. Instructors who are adept at handling online platforms also tend to excel in administering exams, providing feedback, and engaging students in diverse assessment methods. This emphasizes the need for continuous investment in the professional development of educators, equipping them with the necessary technological skills to enhance their teaching efficacy.

The findings also highlight that courses designed with a variety of content delivery and assessment methods yield better student engagement and learning outcomes. This correlation suggests that the quality of online education can be significantly improved by employing diverse teaching strategies, which not only cater to different learning styles but also encourage active participation and deeper understanding of the material.

Negative Correlations and Gender Inclusivity

On the other hand, the study identifies notable challenges related to gender inclusivity in online teaching environments. Instructors who expressed discomfort with teaching mixed-gender groups were less likely to employ diverse teaching methods or fully engage with their students. These findings point to the need for universities to create more inclusive educational environments where all instructors feel comfortable teaching, regardless of the gender composition of their classes.

Strong negative correlations, such as those between reluctance to teach mixed-gender groups and teaching engagement, underscore the importance of addressing these issues through targeted interventions. Workshops and training sessions on gender inclusivity could play a vital role in helping instructors overcome these challenges, fostering a more inclusive and effective online teaching environment.

Institutional Support and Resources

Another key finding of this study is the critical role of institutional support in online teaching. Many instructors reported that their satisfaction with online teaching was closely linked to the availability of technical resources and support services. For example, the stability of internet connectivity and access to necessary devices were found to be essential factors influencing instructors' teaching performance. Without reliable access to these resources, instructors faced significant challenges in delivering high-quality online education.

The development of centralized technical support services is, therefore, crucial for ensuring that instructors have the assistance they need to address technical difficulties promptly. In addition, providing instructors with adequate financial support to cover internet expenses and access to the necessary technology can significantly enhance their teaching capabilities and reduce the burden of online instruction.

Implications for Future Online Learning

The findings of this study have important implications for the future of online education in Kazakhstan and beyond. As online learning continues to evolve, it is essential for higher education institutions to focus on the professional development of instructors, ensuring they are equipped with both the technical skills and pedagogical strategies required for effective online teaching. Furthermore, addressing issues related to gender inclusivity and providing robust institutional support will be key to creating a more equitable and effective online learning environment.

To conclude, this study highlights the complex interplay between technical proficiency, institutional support, and inclusivity in shaping instructors' experiences of online teaching. By addressing the challenges identified in this study and building on the strengths of current practices, higher education institutions can significantly improve the quality of online education, ultimately enhancing both instructor satisfaction and student outcomes.

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